

Competition between built-in polarization and p–n junction field in III-nitride heterostructures

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ABSTRACT

The high built-in polarization field is a fingerprint of III-nitride heterostructures. Alloy composition and doping profile significantly affect the magnitude of the electric field present in subsequent layers, but the sign of the electric field is usually defined by substrate polarity and external bias. Here, we propose to utilize acceptor and donor doping concentrations exceeding 10^{20} cm^{-3} to obtain a high junction field that can solely abolish built-in polarization for a polar (0001) InGaN/GaN quantum well (QW). We have used photoluminescence (PL), time-resolved PL (TRPL), and contactless electroreflectance in order to gain insight into the strength of the electric field present in the grown heterostructures. Good match between expected and measured electric field values was obtained. A dramatic decrease in the luminescence lifetime for a flat QW was confirmed using TRPL. The presented results open a way to realize devices that profit from the low built-in field, like photodetectors, using abundant polar substrates.

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INTRODUCTION

III-nitride light emitters are most commonly obtained along polar and semipolar directions. Consequently, built-in polarization, both spontaneous and piezoelectric, must be considered when simulating and designing III-nitride heterostructures.¹ As it was shown, polarization in nitrides can be utilized to improve the performance of the AlGaN/GaN ultraviolet emitters and InGaN/GaN visible emitters.^{2,3} Polarization field engineering can also be used to affect absorption in p-i-n detectors⁴ and solar cells.^{5,6}

In addition to the alloy composition, the main design parameter of the active region is the quantum well (QW) thickness. For a polar material, it affects transition energies in a much stronger way than in the case of non-polar and semipolar QWs.^{7–9} In the polar case, together with the change in the emission wavelength, the

overlap of the electron–hole wavefunction changes, diminishing transition probabilities for ground states of electrons and holes in relatively thicker QWs.^{10–14} On the other hand, carriers that do not recombine effectively due to low transition probability accumulate at the QW interfaces and screen the built-in polarization field restoring the square-like symmetry of the QW potential and providing a dominant contribution to recombination from higher energy states.¹⁵

The polarity of a particular structure is usually controlled by the crystal symmetry of the substrate used for its growth. For bulk GaN substrates, this binds the resulting polarization with growth conditions and specifics of the optimal surface preparation for each crystallographic direction. However, as we have recently shown, this restriction, at least to some extent, can be lifted to realize vertical

Ga- and N-polar-like structures on Ga-polar substrates by using a buried tunnel-junction.¹⁶ In this approach, the N-polar-like structure is obtained by inverting the current flow direction with respect to the built-in polarization. This approach was used to realize LEDs and laser diodes (LDs).¹⁷

In the general case, the electric field should be treated as vector, but here, since we discuss only the electric field along the growth direction, for simplicity, we treat it as a scalar, where positive values indicate the electric field pointing from the sample's surface downward. Then, in the absence of free carriers, the total electric field in the active part of the structure, F_T , can be written as¹⁸

$$F_T = F_P + F_J(d_i, N_A, N_D) + \frac{V}{d}, \quad (1)$$

where F_P is the polarization field (spontaneous and piezoelectric), F_J is the junction field (caused by a common Fermi level in p-n junction, dependent on d_i , the thickness of the undoped region, and N_A and N_D , p- and n-type doping concentration, respectively), and $\frac{V}{d}$ is the electric field associated with externally applied voltage V and thickness d (total thickness of the undoped and depletion regions). A simplified analytical approach to $F_J(d_i, N_A, N_D)$ dependence on the structure design parameters is given in the [supplementary material](#). In a more general case, the total electric field is further adjusted by the aforementioned screening caused by the presence of free carriers originating from, i.e., residual doping, carrier flow, or optical absorption.^{19,20}

The complexity of the whole issue makes it difficult to present a comprehensive study of the impact of the field on luminescence from such structures. This is one of the reasons why structures grown on non-polar substrates were investigated,²¹ where by definition $F_P = 0$, and by comparison with the same structures grown along a polar direction [see [Fig. 1\(a\)](#) for comparison of the conduction band profile], the impact of the built-in polarization can be inferred. However, it is challenging to obtain comparable structures on different substrates as the alloy composition and point defect creation are known to strongly depend on the growth direction.

Another approach to obtain flatband conditions (the total electric field in a QW equals zero) is to apply negative external bias $\frac{V}{d} = -(F_P + F_J)$.^{22–27} The conduction band profile for this structure with and without bias is shown in [Fig. 1\(b\)](#).

Alternatively, strong Si-doped prelayers below the QW²⁸ or quantum barriers (QBs) on both sides of the QW were used to screen the piezoelectric charges.^{29,30} This idea was further expanded using the n-doping on one side of the QW and p-doping on the other side to generate F_J that would lead to flatband conditions.^{31,32} It has been recently also shown that this approach can reduce both: carrier lifetime and carrier density during the operation of such LEDs.³³

In the present work, we investigate a series of single QW structures surrounded by thin undoped spacers that are further enclosed in a p-n junction. By using high p- and n-type doping levels, we managed to obtain flatband conditions for unprocessed structures, with no external bias. Impact of the increase in p- and n-type doping on the conduction band profile of such structures is presented in [Fig. 1\(c\)](#). This finding proves that extremely high built-in polarization, an intrinsic property of polar III-nitride heterostructures, can be eliminated solely by the junction field.

FIG. 1. Schematic presentation of the conduction band profile as a function of depth for three different structures, each for two conditions: one observed typically and the other where in QW $F_T = 0$. (a) Polar (black) and non-polar (blue) QW without doping, (b) polar QW in p-n junction with moderate doping level under $V = 0$ (black) and $\frac{V}{d} = -(F_P + F_J)$ (green), (c) QW in the p-n junction for moderate (black) and high (orange) doping levels.

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EXPERIMENTAL

All samples in this study were grown by plasma-assisted molecular beam epitaxy to obtain a sharp doping profile, abrupt changes in the alloy composition, and as-grown high hole concentration. Standard effusion cells were used to provide the molecular beam of Ga, In, and Ge. Germanium was used as a donor to enable high n-type carrier concentration close to 100% ionization efficiency.³⁴ To supply magnesium and ensure low background doping, the valved source for corrosive materials was used. Details on growth conditions and used substrates are presented in the [supplementary material](#). We expect ionization efficiency for magnesium in this case to be larger than that obtained for GaN layers,³⁵ which was 4%.

Each investigated sample consists of a single 2.6 nm-thick $\text{In}_{0.17}\text{Ga}_{0.83}\text{N}$ QW sandwiched by two 5 nm undoped $\text{In}_{0.03}\text{Ga}_{0.97}\text{N}$ layers from each side, which will be referred to as quantum barriers (QBs). Such a common active region is further enclosed by $\text{In}_{0.03}\text{Ga}_{0.97}\text{N}$ doped with Mg or Ge from top and bottom, respectively. The same InGaN composition was used around the QW to

TABLE I Parameters of the samples under study.

Sample ID	Doping		AFM RMS 2 × 2 μm ² (nm)	Calculated		CW PL		TRPL		CER	
	N _{Mg} (10 ¹⁹ cm ⁻³)	N _{Ge} (10 ¹⁹ cm ⁻³)		F _{OB} (MV/cm)	F _{OW} (MV/cm)	λ (nm)	FWHM (nm)	I _{peak} (arb. unit)	λ ₀ (t = 0) (nm)	λ ₀ -λ _{0∞} (nm)	F _{OB} (MV/cm)
refQW1 R1155	uid	uid	0.5	-0.26	465	24.1	0.5	472	19	-0.28 ± 0.02	NA
QW2 R1152	1.5	0.8	0.6	-1.7	458	20.4	0.52	461	7	-1.6 ± 0.2	+
QW3 R1160	3	7	0.5	-2.4	451	19.3	1	451	9	-2.3 ± 0.1	-
QW4 R1156	4	20	0.8	-2.6	449	18.6	0.86	449	5	-2.3 ± 0.1	-
QW5 R1167	6	30	0.5	-2.7	441	19	0.4	441	3	-2.8 ± 0.5	-
QW6 R1181	20	60	0.7	-2.8	443	17.2	0.17	444	<1	-2.6 ± 0.1	-
invQW R1163	3	7	0.8	+1.7	478	30	0.11	478	10	NA	NA
NoQW R1161	3	7	0.7	-2.1	415	NA	0.5	NA	NA	-2.2 ± 0.2	NA

ensure a sharp doping profile and no polarization charges except for the QW itself. Intentionally undoped QBs of 5 nm were used to assure negligible residual doping inside the QW that could lead to increased nonradiative recombination for high doping levels. In a previous study,³⁶ a decline in Si and Mg concentrations of 1.9 and 1.7 nm/dec, respectively, were obtained by secondary mass spectroscopy.

Main set of p-n junction samples is extended by adding a fully undoped sample (refQW1) and the sample where the ordering of Mg- and Ge-doped layers is inverted (invQW). The set of QW-containing samples is enriched by the In_{0.03}Ga_{0.97}N-based p-i-n diode with a 12.6 nm-thick undoped region, with no QW (NoQW). Doping levels and additional characterization data are gathered in Table I. The schematic layer structure for each sample is presented in the supplementary material.

Postgrowth quality was investigated using atomic force microscopy (AFM) to investigate possible surface deterioration caused by increased doping. Obtained root mean square (RMS) roughness obtained for 2 × 2 μm² scans is presented in Table I. X-ray diffraction (XRD) was used to confirm similar alloy compositions in all samples.

The built-in electric field present in the structure was investigated employing a photoluminescence experiment (PL) under continuous wave (CW) excitation at 325 nm and 50 W/cm². Time-resolved photoluminescence (TRPL) was measured with a standard PL setup. As an excitation source, the Ti:sapphire oscillator with second harmonic generation crystal and a pulse picker was used to provide ~140 fs-long optical pulses with E_{exc} = 3.14 eV photon energy (~395 nm) and 8 MHz repetition frequency. The average excitation power density was approximately 150 W/cm². The PL emission was dispersed by a 0.3 m-focal length monochromator, and the temporal evolution of the PL signal was detected by a streak camera. The effective time resolution of the system is approximately 20 ps. Contactless electroreflectance (CER)³⁷ measurements were taken at room temperature in a dark configuration. In the CER spectrum, resonant-like features appear at energies corresponding to optical transitions. In the presence of a built-in electric field, as a consequence of the Franz-Keldysh effect, characteristic oscillations (FKOs—Franz-Keldysh oscillations) appear. FKOs can be analyzed to extract a built-in field.^{38,39} The used procedure and more details on the CER setup are presented in the supplementary material.

RESULTS

To show the consequences of the competition between built-in polarization and the p-n junction field, we simulated band diagrams for all samples presented in Table I using one-dimensional Poisson, drift-diffusion, and Schrodinger Solver DDCC-1D.⁴⁰ For the purpose of the presented calculations, activation energies of 10 (Ref. 41) and 190 meV,⁴² independent of dopant concentrations, for n- and p-types, respectively, were used. It should be emphasized that this straightforward assumption overlooks any changes in activation energies or compensation mechanisms for different doping levels, despite its reported significant role at high doping concentrations.^{41,43,44} Even though a lower E_A value increases the hole concentration, it does not transfer into a huge change in F_{OB}. Assuming E_A = 100 meV, instead of 190 meV,

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FIG. 2. Conduction and valence band edges (left axis) and electric field (right axis-green) as a function of depth in the vicinity of the QW in structures: (a) refQW1, (b) QW2, (c) QW6, and (d) invQW7.

FIG. 3. Photoluminescence intensity (gray bars), wavelength (orange diamonds), and full width at half maximum (blue circles) as a function of electric field F_{QW} calculated using a 1D-DDCC simulator.

for sample **QW6** would lead to a difference in expected F_{QB} of -0.06 MV/cm. For each doping concentration, the electric field in the middle of the QW and undoped part of the QB was extracted and denoted as F_{QW} and F_{QB} , respectively. The band diagram and the electric field across the structure for the most distinctive cases are presented in **Fig. 2**. For reference sample **refQW1** [**Fig. 2(a)**] with a typical QW surrounded by unintentionally doped QBs, we obtained an F_{QW} of 2.3 MV/cm. For the case of doping levels ($< 2 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) in the cladding layers [**Fig. 2(b)**], F_{QW} is reduced by more than half (to 1 MV/cm), while F_{QB} increases to a similar value as F_{QW} but with an opposite sign (-1.5 MV/cm). A further increase in the doping level reduces the depletion width, which leads to an increase in the F_{QB} value and reduced F_{QW} , as indicated in **Table I**. It is noticeable by comparing **Figs. 2(b)** and **2(c)**. For the highest considered doping levels [**Fig. 2(c)**], F_j is high enough to completely overcome the built-in F_p , leading to negative F_{QW} values.

To further widen the spectrum of investigated F_{QW} values, we included the **invQW** structure in the comparison [**Fig. 2(d)**]. In this case, p- and n-type doped layers are grown below and on top of the QW region. Inverted ordering of the layers with respect to other structures results in conditions where F_p and F_j are pointing in the same direction and total F_{QW} is almost doubled compared to the **refQW1** structure. For this case, F_{QW} and F_{QB} have the same (positive) sign, resulting in a very shallow potential minimum inside the QW. The CW PL study was conducted for all samples. Obtained intensity, emission wavelength, and full width at half maximum (FWHM) as a function of expected F_{QW} (obtained using DDCC-1D assuming the used doping concentrations) are presented in **Fig. 3**. For F_{QW} higher than 0.5 MV/cm, the PL spectra clearly decrease in the intensity and increase in the FWHM. It can be explained by the quantum-confined Stark effect (QCSE), which causes spatial separation of electron and hole wavefunctions, leading to lower recombination probability and larger FWHM.

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FIG. 4. Time-resolved photoluminescence maps (a), (c), (e), and (g) and spectra (b), (d), (f), and (h) as a function of wavelength. Red dashed line on luminescence maps shows the peak maximum. Solid and dashed red lines on spectra mark the center of the shortest and the longest emission spectra. Numbers next to spectra presented in (b), (d), (f), and (h) denote the time after the pulse for which it was extracted.

FIG. 5. (a) Contactless electroreflectance (CER) spectra of undoped structure (refQW1), QW in p-n junction (QW2, QW3, QW6), and reference p-n junction with no QW (NoQW). The QW-related transition is around 2.8 eV (blue-shaded area) and the QB one around 3.2 eV (violet-shaded area). Extreme values used to calculate the built-in electric field F_{QB} are indexed with integer numbers ($n = 1, 2, 3, 4$). (b) Values of the electric field in QB (F_{QB}) extracted from CER as a function of field obtained from simulations. Gray line is a guide to the eye.

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This is also consistent with the observed shift of emission wavelength. Higher F_{QW} leads to the deepening of the potential well for electrons and holes, leading to lower transition energy and probability.¹⁴ For $F_{QW} = 0.3$ MV/cm, we obtained the maximum emission intensity that decreased for lower F_{QW} values. Even though we still expect that the wavefunction overlap increases in this range, which is suggested by the shortening of the observed emission wavelength, the emission intensity is dominated by another effect. Increased carrier escape is expected for a relatively shallow QW surrounded by a high F_{QB} region.³² That is why we attribute a low emission intensity for a flatband QW and **invQW** [see Figs. 2(c) and 2(d), respectively] to enhanced carrier escape induced by the thinning of a triangular barrier near a QW with increasing F_{QB} .

More information can be derived from the analysis of TRPL experiments.^{12,14,28} It is expected that after a short pulse excitation, the photo-injected carriers will affect the electric field inside a QW due to the carrier density-dependent screening effect. Moreover, the effect will evolve since the photo-injected carrier density undergoes radiative and nonradiative recombination. Therefore, TRPL gives indirect information on F_{QW} . Figure 4 presents TRPL data for four distinctive samples. First, we focus on the time evolution of the emission wavelength. For each structure, we can distinguish between two extreme positions denoted by λ_0 and λ_∞ that identified the PL peak intensity position just after and at a much longer time after excitation, respectively. These are collected in Table I. Similarly to the CW PL experiment, λ_0 decreases with increasing doping. Upon recombination, the emission wavelength, which starts at λ_0 due to instantaneous initial field screening, shifts toward λ_∞ , at which the pre-excitation field condition is restored. Therefore, as shown before,^{12–14} the spectral shift $\lambda_0 - \lambda_\infty$ allows to assess non-directly the relative electric field evolution inside a QW. It should roughly scale with F_{QW} , a clear consequence of the dynamic QCSE. For **refQW1**, the shift amounts to 19 nm, which drops to below 1 nm in the case of the most strongly doped **QW6** sample. Moreover, the QCSE also impacts the recombination lifetime for **refQW1–QW6**, leading to a shorter lifetime for the lower F_{QW} . Interestingly, the TRPL signal for **invQW** is not following this trend. Despite the highest F_{QW} value in this case, it has the shortest observed PL lifetime. However, for this structure, F_{QW} points in the same direction as F_{QB} opening the beforementioned carrier escape channel, which is detrimental to the PL lifetime. A low PL intensity under CW excitation and a very short PL lifetime observed by TRPL are a fingerprint of the dominant role of carrier escape for **invQW**.

The CER experiment was carried out to more directly probe built-in polarization in the investigated structures (see Fig. 5). The results were compared to those obtained from DDCC-1D simulations. FKO spectrally appeared above the $\text{In}_{0.03}\text{Ga}_{0.97}\text{N}$ bandgap, marked by a violet-shaded area in Fig. 5(a). The analysis of FKO conducted using the procedure used before^{38,39} and shown in the supplementary material allowed us to derive F_{QB} in **refQW1–QW6** samples. In addition, we performed the CER experiment on the **NoQW** sample grown to investigate the built-in electric field in the absence of a QW layer. The field magnitudes obtained by the FKO analysis are collected in Table I. It should be noted that the experiment was proven unsuccessful for the **invQW** sample, where the high electron concentration in the top layer efficiently screens the

external field.⁴⁵ F_{QB} values [Fig. 5(b)] extracted from the CER study performed on all obtained samples follow the values expected from simulations presented in Fig. 2. Another interesting observation is related to the optical transition in the QW (close to 2.8 eV). For **refQW1**, this transition was not observed in CER, due to high F_{QW} , leading to a low electron–hole wavefunction overlap in this case. For the **QW2** sample, the junction field F_j significantly decreases F_{QW} , leading to higher transition probability and the associated feature emerges in the CER spectrum. Surprisingly, for relatively low doping used in **QW3**, the transition in the CER spectrum changes the phase in respect to that for **QW2**. The phase for QW transition is schematically marked in Fig. 5(a) by “+” and “–” signs for **QW2** and **QW3–6**, respectively. For samples **QW4–6**, as expected for even higher doping levels, it stays the same as for **QW3**. This is a straightforward argument supporting experimentally⁴⁶ that the sign of F_{QW} could be changed using only F_j , without an external electric field.

CONCLUSIONS

Strong built-in polarization is one of the most distinctive features of III-nitride heterostructures. It is often regarded as a parameter defined by the used substrate. Within that scheme, to investigate quantum wells with lower or no built-in field, semi- or nonpolar GaN substrates need to be used. Since the use of different crystallographic planes leads to different growth conditions and point defect incorporation, a direct comparison between structures with a different built-in field is nontrivial.

Here, we proposed a straightforward approach to use the p–n junction field to counterbalance the field originating from polarization charges. When the doping concentration is varied, the electric field in the quantum well can be tailored significantly. By introducing doping concentrations exceeding 10^{20} cm^{-3} , we were able to present an inverted direction of the built-in electric field in such structures.

Optical properties of III-nitride heterostructures as a function of built-in electric field were compared. The impact of the QCSE on the transition energy and photoluminescence dynamics was discussed. The electric field obtained from CER matches the values expected for the electric field in surrounding barriers.

To further increase the accessible range of F_j , which can be used to flatten bands for even higher indium content QWs, a thinner undoped region should be used. For such structures, extreme care should be also devoted to limiting the background doping level that can lead to nonradiative recombination in a QW.

The presented results pave the way toward a new platform for investigating the built-in electric field and its impact on the optical transition in III-nitride heterostructures. Polar p–n diodes with a quantum well with no built-in field offer interesting potential for high efficiency, low operating voltage photodetectors.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

See the supplementary material for additional data regarding the sample structure, as well as details on AFM and XRD characterizations. Furthermore, we present a comprehensive description of the procedures employed to extract the electric field from the CER measurements.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Henryk Turski: Conceptualization (lead); Funding acquisition (lead); Methodology (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – original draft (lead). **Mikolaj Chlipala:** Conceptualization (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Software (equal); Visualization (lead); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Ewelina Zdanowicz:** Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Visualization (supporting); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Ernest Rogowicz:** Investigation (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Grzegorz Muziol:** Conceptualization (supporting); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (supporting). **Joanna Moneta:** Investigation (supporting); Validation (supporting); Writing – review & editing (supporting). **Szymon Grzanka:** Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal). **Marcin Kryśko:** Investigation (equal). **Marcin Syperek:** Formal analysis (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Robert Kudrawiec:** Conceptualization (supporting); Methodology (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Czesław Skierbiszewski:** Funding acquisition (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (supporting); Writing – review & editing (supporting).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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